

Social

**EMPOWERMENT OF BOGA TEACHER EMPOWERMENT
MANAGEMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SANTRI
ENTREPRENEURS IN THE PESANTREN NURUL IMAN, THE MUARA
JAMBI DISTRICT, JAMBI PROVINSI**

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Abstract

Tata Boga is one of the entrepreneurship of students at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School which aims to equip students with entrepreneurial science in cooking. This study uses a descriptive qualitative approach. By using the method of observation, interviews and documentation. Data analysis uses the Miles and Huberman models, while the data validity technique uses triangulation. The results of the study were: The leadership of the Islamic boarding school planned the facilities and infrastructure before identifying the teacher, delegating the task of teaching cooking to qualified teachers, and giving curriculum autonomy, scheduling schedules and funding. In organizing activities, the head of the lodge places himself as a supervisor, and instructs the principal as the supervisor and person in charge, the chairman of the entrepreneurial coordinator as the driver, and the teacher as the implementer. In the implementation activities the leader instructs the principal so that the teacher prepares the syllabus and lesson plan, optimizes himself / herself to become a counselor and instructor, completes the class administration, and develops evaluation of learning. The supervisory activities include direct supervision by looking directly at the implementation of indirect learning and supervision activities by looking through curriculum documents.

Keywords: Empowerment Management; Teacher; Students Entrepreneurship.

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1. Introduction

Islamic boarding schools are one form of Islamic educational institutions that aim to form perfect Muslim human beings (*insan kamil*)¹. Ramayulis² further stated that human beings are human beings who have the face of Qur'an, the achievement of people who have religious, cultured and scientific dimensions. As an educational institution, Islamic boarding schools are currently experiencing a lot of development both in aspects of the curriculum, facilities and infrastructure, as well as human Resources. From some of these changes, the head of the Islamic boarding school needs to make adjustments in planning, organizing, coordinating and controlling the implementation of educational activities that take place so as to create a conducive boarding school environment and learning objectives can be achieved effectively and efficiently. Activities that include planning, organizing, implementing and monitoring are also referred to as management activities. This as mentioned by Nawawi in Onisimus Amtu³ management is a series of activities to achieve organizational goals that begin with planning (planning), organizing (organizing) implementation (actuating), supervision (controlling), and budgeting (budgeting). Management activities in administering education are very important to do, including the provision of entrepreneurship knowledge. To give birth to students who have qualified religious knowledge and have a number of entrepreneurial competencies, the leadership of Islamic boarding schools need to plan, organize, coordinate and supervise so that the goals of developing entrepreneurship can be achieved effectively and efficiently.

According to J.B. Say in Veerabhadrapa Havinal (1803)⁴ "An entrepreneur is one who combines the land of one, the labor of another and the capital of another, and thus produces a product. By selling the product in the market, he pays interest on capital, rent on land and wages to laborers and what remains is his profit. In contrast to the meaning of entrepreneurship which refers to business actors, the meaning of entrepreneurship is more to the process of forming, applying an innovation to an entrepreneur. According to Hisrich, Peters & Shepherd in Moh Alifuddin and Mashur Razak⁵ entrepreneurship is the process of creating something new value, using time and effort, bearing financial, physical, and social risks that accompany it, but receiving monetary rewards and personal satisfaction and freedom.

Student entrepreneurship needs to be developed because not all Students will become leader of the islamic boarding school, by providing entrepreneurship knowledge students are expected to be able to survive in the midst of society and even be able to empower the people around them.

The results of observations, interviews and documentation at the Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School included: Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School providing students with a science of culinary entrepreneurship, is one of the entrepreneurship subjects developed in the Nurul Iman

¹ Nur Komariah, *Pemberdayaan Guru Pondok Pesantren dalam Membangun Kewirausahaan Santri di Pondok Pesantren Provinsi Jambi, (Studi Multi Kasus Pada Pondok Pesantren Nurul Iman Kabupaten Muara Jambi, Pondok Pesantren Raudhatul Mujawwidin Kabupaten Tebo, dan Pondok Pesantren Al-Fattah Kabupaten Sarolangun)* 2019. Program Manajemen Pendidikan Islam, Universitas Islam Negeri STS Jambi), p.1.

² Ramayulis, *Ilmu Pendidikan Islam* (Jakarta: Kalam Mulia, 2013), p. 101.

³ Onisimus Amtu, *Manajemen Pendidikan di Era Otonomi Daerah* (Bandung: Alfabeta, 2013), p. 4.

⁴ Veerabhadrapa Havinal, *Management and Entrepreneurship* (New Delhi: One Word, 2009), p. 96.

⁵ Moh. Alifuddin dan Mashur Razak, *Kewirausahaan: Teori dan Aplikasi* (Jakarta: Magna Script Publishing, 2015), p. 26.

Islamic Boarding School which is most in demand by students. many students who are interested, boarding schools are faced with new problems, namely the limited facilities and infrastructure. It can be seen that the cooking laboratories are not equipped with drains and contact boxes. In addition, in terms of cooking equipment it is still very limited, namely there are two preparation tables, as well as a number of cooking utensils arranged in two storage cabinets. So that in the implementation of practical learning activities students must take turns using cooking equipment.⁶ Furthermore, K said, In addition to limited equipment, catering classes were also faced with limited practical funds.

From the data above, the writer can identify two main problems, namely: learning facilities and infrastructure are still very limited and the funding of students practice is limited. From identifying these problems, the authors want to examine more deeply about "Management of Islamic Boarding Schools in Developing Students Entrepreneurship at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara Jambi Regency".

2. Problems, Objectives, and Usability

2.1. Problems

- How is the planning of Islamic boarding schools to build students entrepreneurship at the Jambi Province Islamic Boarding School in Muara Jambi Regency?
- How to organize Islamic boarding schools in building students entrepreneurship at Islamic Boarding School in Jambi Province, Muara Jambi Regency?
- How to coordinate Islamic boarding schools in building student entrepreneurship at Islamic Boarding School in Jambi Province, Muara Jambi Regency?
- What is the supervision of Islamic boarding schools in building student entrepreneurship at Islamic Boarding School in Jambi Province, Muara Jambi Regency?

2.2. Objectives and Benefits of Research

The purpose of this research is:

- Want to know how to plan the empowerment of Islamic boarding school teachers in building entrepreneurship in a cookery at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara Jambi Regency, Jambi Province?
- Want to know how to organize the empowerment of Islamic boarding school teachers in building entrepreneurship in catering at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara Jambi Regency, Jambi Province?
- Want to know how to coordinate the empowerment of teachers of Islamic boarding schools in building entrepreneurship in cooking at the Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara Jambi Regency, Jambi Province?
- Want to know how to supervise the empowerment of Islamic boarding school teachers in building entrepreneurship in catering at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara Jambi Regency, Jambi Province?

⁶ Observation at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara District Jambi Province Jambi October 15 2018.

2.3. Benefits of Research

The benefits that can be taken from this study are as follows:

Practically, this research is expected to be able to provide benefits to the boarding school leaders to plan, organize, coordinate, and oversee the development of entrepreneurship activities of students in the Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara Jambi Regency, Jambi Province. Theoretically, this research is a contribution of thought and input regarding the management of Islamic boarding schools in building entrepreneurship of students at the Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Jambi Province.

3. Thinking Framework and Research Methods

3.1. Thinking Framework

Management of Islamic Boarding Schools

Islamic Boarding Schools are the oldest Islamic educational institutions in Indonesia which are the result of Indonesian cultural products.⁷ At the beginning of its development, Islamic boarding schools only taught religious books under the guidance of scholars.⁸ But as the development of Islamic boarding schools has now undergone transformation by developing aspects of the curriculum, human resources and facilities and infrastructure. Therefore, in its management, good management is needed so that goals can be achieved effectively and efficiently.

According to Andrew J. Dubrin,⁹ management is the process of using organizational resources to achieve organizational goals based on the functions of planning, decision making, organizing, leadership, and supervision. Mean while Gareth R. Jones and Jennifer M. George¹⁰ Management is a process of planning, organizing, leading, and controlling human resources and others to achieve their organizational goals effectively and efficiently.

From the opinion above, it can be concluded that the management of Islamic boarding schools is a number of educational activities in Islamic boarding schools that start from planning, organizing, coordinating and supervising to achieve educational goals in Islamic boarding schools.

Management Process

Plan

Planning is the first step in management activities. There are three activities that must be considered by the head of the boarding school to plan teacher empowerment activities, namely: planning aspects related to the ability of the teacher, planning aspects related to the condition of the organization and planning aspects related to organizational policy.¹¹

⁷ Amin Haedari, *Transformasi Pesantren*, (Jakarta: Lekdis, 2006), p. 3.

⁸ Mardiya, *Kepemimpinan Kiai dalam Memelihara Budaya Organisasi*, (Malang: Aditya Media, 2015), p. 15.

⁹ Andrew J. Dubrin, *Essential Of Management* (Ohio, South Wesiren, 1990), p.20.

¹⁰ Gareth R. Jones, Jennifer M. George., *Essentials of Contemporary Management*, (New York: McGraw-hill). p. 5.

¹¹ Ahmad Susanto, *Manajemen Peningkatan Kinerja Guru* (Jakarta: Kencana, 2016), p.43-44.

Organizing Teacher Empowerment

Organizing can be interpreted as the efforts of leaders in determining human resources into their duties or roles to achieve organizational goals. Furthermore, Yati Siti Mulyati and Aan Komariah¹² detailing organizational activities into several activities, namely: (1) determine the resources and activities needed to achieve organizational goals, (2) design and develop work groups by determining human resources capable of achieving organizational goals, (3) assigning someone with a responsibility answer or task that has been determined, (4) delegate authority to human resources related to freedom in carrying out tasks.

Teacher Empowerment Implementation

Implementation of the empowerment of teachers is an activity of the application of the plans that have been established so as to achieve the desired objectives. To obtain optimal results and in accordance with the stated goals of teachers should be guided by the planning that has been set in terms of both the use of time and the use of budgetary empowerment. According to Ahmad Susanto¹³ teacher empowerment implementation include: the empowerment of teachers as a demonstrator, empowering teacher as managers of the classroom, the teacher as a facilitator of empowerment, empowerment of teachers as counselors, empowering teachers as administrators and empowering teachers as evaluators.

Teacher Empowerment Evaluation

Teacher empowerment evaluation is a process of measuring and assessing which is directed at measuring the extent to which the teacher's success in carrying out his duties and obligations properly.¹⁴ Teachers who have the power to work are teachers who have a good understanding of their functions and duties as educators.

Definition of Entrepreneurship

The term entrepreneurship itself actually starts from French, namely "entrepreneur" which means adventurer, creator and business manager. J.B. Say in Veerabhadrapa Havinal¹⁵ (1803) he argues that "*an entrepreneur is one who combines the land of one, the labor of another and capital of yet another, and thus produces a product. By selling the product in the market, he pays interest on capital, rent on land and wages to laborers and what remains is his/her profit*".

In contrast to entrepreneurs who refer to business people, according to Chandra S. Mishra and Ramona K. Zachary¹⁶ entrepreneurship is an entrepreneurial process that is driven by entrepreneurial intentions and desires for entrepreneurial rewards, processes that involve identifying entrepreneurial opportunities to build entrepreneurial competencies to finally appropriate entrepreneurial rewards. This opinion is in line with the opinion of Saban Echdar¹⁷. Entrepreneurship is a discipline that studies the values and abilities of a person's behavior in facing life's challenges to obtain opportunities with various risks they may faced.

¹² Yati Siti Mulyati dan Aan Komariah, *Manajemen Pendidikan* (Bandung: Alfabeta, 2009), p. 94.

¹³ Ahmad Susanto, *Op. Cit.*, p.43-44.

¹⁴ Ahmad Susanto, *Op.Cit.*, hal 43-47.

¹⁵ Veerabhadrapa Havinal, *Management and Entrepreneurship* (New Delhi: One Word, 2009), p. 96.

¹⁶ Chandra S, Mishra and Ramona K. *The Theory of Entrepreneurship: Creating and Sustaining Entrepreneurial Value.* (New York: Palgrave Macmilan, 2013)., p. 16.

¹⁷ Saban Echdar, *Manajemen Entrepreneurship Kiat Sukses Menjadi Wirausaha* (Yogyakarta: Andi dan Nobel School of Business, tt), p. 2.

From several opinions it can be concluded that entrepreneurship is a process of building entrepreneurial competencies so that someone is tested and deserves to be an entrepreneur after going through the learning process both theoretically and practically.

Entrepreneurship Competence

Martin Lackéus¹⁸ in his journal, that to provide students with entrepreneurial knowledge there are at least three types of knowledge that prospective entrepreneurs must have before finally starting a business, namely knowledge, skills and attitudes. Furthermore Yuyus Suryana¹⁹ said, There are several skills that must be possessed by an entrepreneur, namely: 1) Conceptual skills set strategy and take into account risks, 2) Lead and manage skills, 3) Technical skills in business fields, 4) Communication and interaction skills, 5) Creative skills create added value.

Forms of Business

Before starting a business, first determine what field of business to pursue. As for the forms of business that can be cultivated for beginners in accordance with their talents and interests, especially for small and medium enterprises, among others, as follows: Beauty sector, skills sector, consulting sector, industrial sector, mining sector, marine sector, fisheries sector, agro sector business, trade sector, education sector, printing sector, arts sector, health sector and other business sectors.²⁰

3.2. Research Methods

This study uses a qualitative approach through the perspective of education. This research is emic perspective. Taking the social situation at the Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara Jambi Regency, Jambi Province with data sources from the heads of Islamic boarding schools, principals, entrepreneurial coordinators, teachers, and students. The data collection methods used were observation, interviews and documentation with the subject of research covering all elements related to the management of entrepreneurship development in the Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara Jambi Regency. Next to analyze the data, the author uses the Miles and Huberman data analysis model, is the activity of analyzing data that is carried out interactively and takes place continuously until complete, so that the data is saturated. The activities consist of: data reduction (data reduction), presentation of data (data display) verification (conclusion drawing)²¹

4. Research result

4.1. Planning

For Teacher Governance Empowerment There are several steps taken by the leadership of Islamic boarding schools to empower culinary teachers, namely: (1) preparing facilities and infrastructure for culinary entrepreneurship, (2) identifying teachers who have entrepreneurial skills in cooking and delegating the task of teaching cooking to teachers who has the qualifications as an educator. In this aspect the teacher of entrepreneurship has a Bachelor of Education (S1) education

¹⁸ Martin Lackéus, *Entrepreneurship in education: What, Why, When, How*, (Paris, OECD, 2015), p.9.

¹⁹ Yuyus Suryana, *Kewirausahaan: Pendekatan Karakteristik Wirausahawan Sukses*. (Jakarta: Kencana. 2014), p. 79

²⁰ Kasmir, *Kewirausahaan*, (Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada, 2014), p. 44-47.

²¹ Djam'an Satori & Aan Komariah, *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*, (Bandung: Alfabeta, 2014), p. 39.

qualification, and (3) gives confidence to the teacher to develop the curriculum, manage the practice fund and the authority to determine the teaching schedule in accordance with the ability and adequacy of the teacher²²

Based on observations, it is known that the leadership of the Islamic boarding school has planned the empowerment of teachers by completing a 35 M2 culinary laboratory unit equipped with two cabinets storing cooking utensils and their equipment, two preparation table units and two gas stove units and tubes. Cooking labor is not provided with contact boxes and water channels.²³

From the observation and interview data above, it can be concluded that the head of the Islamic boarding school has planned the empowerment of culinary teachers by preparing facilities and infrastructure, then identifying teachers, and delegating teaching assignments to teachers who are qualified as culinary teachers, namely Bachelor of Education. To overcome the limitations of these facilities and infrastructure the boarding school boarding schools make policies that support the empowerment of teachers to carry out entrepreneurial development activities for students by providing autonomy in aspects of teaching schedules, curriculum development and cooking funding.

4.2. Organizing Cooking Teacher Empowerment

The head of the boarding school together with the principal and the teacher council form a work team consisting of entrepreneurship teachers as the implementation of entrepreneurship development for students, the head of the self-development coordinator as the leader in implementing entrepreneurship development, the principal as supervisor and chairperson or the boarding school leader.²⁴

Based on observations, it is known that to improve the performance of entrepreneurship teachers at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School, the head of the Islamic boarding school directs one teacher to be the head of the self-development coordinator who provides guidance to teachers who have not qualified as educators and collects syllabi and lesson plans learning activities take place.²⁵

The organizing activities mentioned above are in accordance with the opinions of Yati Siti Mulyati and Aan Komariah²⁶ that organizing activities are activities to determine the resources and activities needed by the organization, design and develop work groups, by determining human resources capable of achieving organizational goals, (3) assigning someone with a defined responsibility or task, (4) delegating authority to human resources related to freedom in carrying out tasks.

²² SH, leader of Islamic Boarding School, Interview, Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara Jambi Regency, October 2018.

²³ Observation at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara District Jambi Province Jambi October 15 2018.

²⁴ IG, School leader, Interview at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara Jambi Regency Jambi Province, 18 October 2018.

²⁵ Observation at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara District Jambi Province Jambi October 15 2018.

²⁶ Yati Siti Mulyati dalam Tim Dosen Administrasi Pendidikan Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia, Manajemen Pendidikan, (Bandung: Alfabeta, 2009), p. 94.

4.3. Implementation of Teacher Empowerment

The following is the implementation of teacher empowerment activities to build entrepreneurship in the catering at Islamic Boarding School Nurul Iman.

4.3.1. *Instruct Culinary Teachers to Compile Syllabus and Lesson Plans.*

According to A²⁷, the head of the Islamic boarding school instructs all teachers to follow all the education policies of the Ministry of Religion of RI and from the Ministry of Education and Culture including policies to form syllabus and lesson plans and make them guidelines in cooking learning activities. Syllabus and RPP are scattered to entrepreneurship teachers before the implementation of learning and pursuing activities takes place. Based on observations²⁸, the teacher of cookery mastered the material taught, this was seen when the teacher was able to answer every question that was asked to the teacher regarding the new recipe delivered. In organizing learning, the teacher often uses question and answer methods, lectures, presentations and group work. Learning activities take place actively, creatively, effectively and pleasantly.

4.3.2. *Provide Trust in Managing the Class Effectively and Efficiently*

To optimize the role of teachers in catering in classroom management, the leadership of Islamic boarding schools makes several policies including giving autonomy in aspects of curriculum, funding and teaching schedules (time allocation). In the curriculum aspect, the head of the Islamic boarding school provides flexibility for the teacher to develop the curriculum, in this case the entrepreneurship teacher develops a cooking curriculum from the Ministry of Education and Culture, and complies with market interest.²⁹ In its efforts to build entrepreneurship for students, teachers not only teach theories about cooking, but teachers also develop skills and develop entrepreneurial attitudes of students³⁰

From some of the explanations above, it can be concluded that the head of Nurul Iman Islamic boarding school optimizes the teacher's role to manage the class effectively and efficiently by giving autonomy in aspects of curriculum, funding, and teaching schedules. With the granting of this autonomy, teachers are able to optimize the class to equip students with knowledge about entrepreneurship, skills and attitudes as entrepreneurs.

4.3.3. *Providing Flexibility in Utilizing Learning Facilities and Infrastructure*

Based on the observation³¹ that the teacher of cooking at the Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School has not been supported by adequate learning facilities and infrastructure. Cooking labor has not been supported by contact boxes and waterways. So that students use the contact contacts in the boarding school hall which is located not far from the catering laboratories, besides the cooking

²⁷ A, Ketua Koordinator Pengembangan Diri, Wawancara, Pondok Pesantren Nurul Iman Kabupaten Muara Jambi, September 2017.

²⁸ Observation at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara District Jambi Province Jambi October 15 2018.

²⁹ K, Cook Teacher, Interview, Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara Jambi Regency, 15 October 2018

³⁰ Observation at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara District Jambi Province Jambi October 15 2018.

³¹ Observation at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara District Jambi Province Jambi October 15 2018.

equipment is still very limited, namely two gas stove units along with gas cylinders, two preparation table units, a blackboard, a teacher desk unit, one unit of teacher chairs and cooking utensils arranged in two cupboards.

The limitations of cooking facilities and infrastructure are one of the obstacles. for teachers to organize efficient learning activities. Learning activities require more time than other subjects because students must take advantage of learning facilities and infrastructure. In every learning and teaching process, students are able to produce five kinds of recipes and sell them to other female students, then the benefits are used to learn the next culinary practice.³² In line with the results of the interview, based on the documentation study, it was understood that the allocation of cooking learning time began at 09.00 until 15.00 WIB. Meanwhile in other entrepreneurship subjects, it is known to start at 09.00-11.00 WIB.³³

From the information above, the author can conclude that to overcome the limitations of facilities and infrastructure for cooking at Islamic Boarding Schools in Nurul Iman, the leadership of Islamic boarding schools provides flexibility for teachers to utilize facilities and infrastructure in Islamic boarding schools, as well as leaders of boarding schools. provide a time allocation that is in accordance with the needs of the teacher in order to achieve learning goals. so that with the limited facilities and infrastructure, the teacher is able to achieve the learning objectives, namely the students is able to produce as many as five kinds of cakes for each unit of the learning process, and market their products to other Islamic boarding schools.

4.3.4. Optimizing the Role of the Teacher as a Counselor or Instructor

To optimize the role of the teacher as an instructor, the head of the Islamic boarding school gives the teacher the freedom to take advantage of the time according to the needs of the teacher and gives the authority to utilize the facilities available at the Islamic Boarding School, as well as giving confidence to the teacher to develop and develop a curriculum for cooking.³⁴

In line with the interview above, it is known that one form of teacher commitment in building entrepreneurship of students is seen in the efforts of teachers in conducting learning and teaching activities. with limited facilities and infrastructure teachers are able to achieve learning goals. In this case the teacher utilizes the extra time given by the head of the boarding school to achieve the learning goals.

From the information above, it can be concluded that the head of the Islamic boarding school optimizes the teacher's role in maximizing the teacher in carrying out his role as a mentor by providing sufficient time to teach, freedom in planning and designing the curriculum to be delivered and providing flexibility to utilize supporting facilities and infrastructure. In its implementation the teacher has made the most of the time that the teacher comes earlier than the

³²K, Cook Teacher, Interview, Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara Jambi Regency, 15 October 2018.

³³Documentation, Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara Jambi Regency, 15 October 2018.

³⁴SH, leader of Islamic Boarding School, Interview, Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara Jambi Regency, October 2018.

specified time and utilizes the extra time given so that the teacher does not only provide culinary knowledge in theory, but the teacher is able to provide culinary knowledge in terms of practice and attitude as entrepreneurship in the field of cooking.

4.3.5. *Optimizing the Teacher's Role in Administrative Aspects*

To find out the success of culinary learning, recording activities are needed such as a list of values, the presence of students, class agenda books, syllabus, lesson plans, and others. Discipline and regularity in the data collection is very necessary for the needs of teachers, students and school archives. Based on observations³⁵, it is known that the head of the Islamic boarding school instructs every teacher to complete the class administration and provides a format for absent students and a list of students values. This is as stated by K that every teacher is required to complete the class administration such as the absence of the student book, class agenda book, syllabus and lesson plan.

From the information above, it can be concluded that the leadership of the Islamic boarding school optimizes the role of the teacher in the administrative aspects by instructing the teacher to prepare the teaching tools before the learning activities take place and provide a format for absenteeism and assessment of student learning outcomes.

4.3.6. *Optimize Leadership*

SH³⁶ said, All the students who want to get the blessing in studying their legal obligations respect their teachers. Teachers in boarding schools are parents who have the responsibility to educate, guide and teach. Therefore, the students who hurts his teacher will be hindered by his knowledge. No teacher or leader of the islamic boarding school should be respected by all students, even children from teachers, siblings or teachers, even if students should give their respect for the blessings of knowledge learned from his teacher.

Based on observations³⁷, it was seen that all students followed all instructed by the teacher, with limited facilities and infrastructure the teacher was able to master the class, the students calmly and regularly waited for their group to learn cooking practices. Even looks familiar atmosphere, even helping each other between groups with other groups.

Based on the information above, the writer concludes that the head of the Islamic boarding school is able to optimize the role of the teacher as a leader in the class through creating a culture of respect for the teacher, placing the position of the teacher after the parents who must be obeyed and respected by the students. So that in its implementation the teacher is able to organize the class well, the students follows every instruction from his teacher.

³⁵ Observation at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara District Jambi Province Jambi October 15 2018.

³⁶ SH, leader of Islamic Boarding School, Interview, Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara Jambi Regency, October 2018.

³⁷ Observation at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara District Jambi Province Jambi October 15 2018.

4.3.7. *Optimizing Self-Efficacy*

Based on the results of the interview, it is known that the teacher's empowerment in carrying out his duties is not limited because the honorarium is received, but for teachers of Islamic boarding schools it is a form of worship so that with the mindset the teacher has strong self-efficacy and influences teacher empowerment in carrying out his role as an educator. This was conveyed by the culinary teacher as follows: "Besides I like the field of cooking, I also feel called to give a briefing to the students about the importance of halal food again, besides I teach this is a form of worship because of Allah SWT."

From the information above, it can be seen that the heads of Islamic boarding schools provide self-efficacy to each teacher so that teaching does not only make money as a goal, but it is more noble that teaching is a form of jihad to Allah and expecting a nobler return to Allah SWT. In its implementation the teacher teaches with sincerity as a form of obedience to Allah SWT. The teaching teacher does not only complete the tasks given by the principal and the head of the Islamic boarding school, but more than that the teacher teaches sincerity and devotion to Allah SWT.

4.3.8. *Optimizing the Role of The Teacher to Carry Out His Role in Developing Evaluation of Learning*

Evaluation needs to be held for each teacher to know the extent to which learning objectives can be achieved. To be able to optimize the role of the teacher in carrying out his role as an evaluator, the head of the Islamic boarding school gives confidence to each teacher to give an assessment, compile the questions of the Middle Semester Exam and the Final Semester Test.³⁸ Furthermore, based on observations seen before organizing learning activities, culinary teachers first provide apperception by asking for new recipes to be delivered to students after that the teacher gives new material with photocopying media which contains new recipes to be learned by students. In the final stage of the culinary learning process activities, each students was assigned to present the results of the production to find out the taste, texture of the food, and how to present it before the students marketed their cake products to other boarding schools.³⁹

From the explanation above, it can be seen that the head of the Islamic boarding school has optimized the role of the teacher as an evaluator by giving confidence to provide assessment, making questions about UTS and UAS. In the implementation of the teacher the teacher has developed a good evaluation of learning, conducting a diagnostic evaluation to determine the teaching material to be delivered, formative evaluation to find out the achievement of learning objectives and summative evaluation to know the results and progress of students in participating in learning activities. While welding teachers, carpentry teachers and fashion teachers have not yet developed a diagnostic evaluation and formative evaluation.

³⁸ IG, School leader, Interview at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara Jambi Regency Jambi Province, 18 October 2018.

³⁹ Observation at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara District Jambi Province Jambi October 15 2018.

4.4. Supervision of Teacher Empowerment in the Development of Students Entrepreneurship

According to IG⁴⁰, Supervision of teacher empowerment at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School is carried out by the heads of Islamic boarding schools, principals and heads of self-development coordinators. Technically, the head of the Islamic boarding school sees directly to labor how the implementation of learning activities, sometimes I also see firsthand how the learning process of catering to know if there are obstacles faced by teachers in developing students entrepreneurship, in addition supervision is also seen from teacher learning devices, while the head of the self-development coordinator conducts supervision through learning tools, ensures that teachers teach with good preparation, there are no obstacles or obstacles in the implementation of learning activities both in aspects of learning material, funding or facilities and infrastructure, and teaching schedules.

In line with the IG, K⁴¹ said, sometimes the heads of Islamic boarding schools and principals see firsthand how the production process takes place and ask what obstacles are faced, and provide solutions either through teacher council meetings or directly such as the use of contact boxes and water ways . Based on data from observations, interviews and documentation, there are several indicators that become the benchmarks for the success of empowering teachers to build students entrepreneurship, namely: a. teacher's ability, b. ability of the teacher's positive attitude towards the profession, and c. teacher's ability to socialize.

4.4.1. Basic Teacher Abilities

Based on observations⁴² it is known that teacher teaching teachers are guided by RPP. The teacher divides the existing students into several groups to complete a recipe that has been prepared in advance. With a variety of limitations on facilities and infrastructure teachers are able to create an active, creative, effective and enjoyable learning environment.

According to F⁴³, Learning cooking is very pleasant, every culinary teacher meeting provides the latest recipes, the material starts from the introduction of healthy food, how to choose healthy food ingredients until the introduction stage of food processing and when students of class XI have studied cake for events birthday party and marriage.⁴⁴ Furthermore, based on the results of the observation, the teacher gives the pretest at the beginning of the learning activity. Furthermore, K said, to find out the achievement of the learning objectives I asked the students to present the results of the production to find out the taste, texture and way of presentation. In addition, the assessment of students was also determined from the UTS and UAS "⁴⁵

⁴⁰ IG, School leader, Interview at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara Jambi Regency Jambi Province, 18 October 2018.

⁴¹ K, Cook Teacher, Interview, Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara District Jambi Province Jambi October 15 2018.

⁴² Observation at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara District Jambi Province Jambi October 15 2018.

⁴³ F, Students, Interview, Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara District Jambi Province Jambi October 15 2018.

⁴⁴ F, Students, Interview, Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara District Jambi Province Jambi October 15 2018.

⁴⁵ Observation at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara District Jambi Province Jambi October 15 2018.

From the data above, it can be concluded that the cook teacher has the basic ability as an educator, namely: (a) Cooking teacher completes his teaching assignments with syllabus and lesson plans and (b) provides diagnostic, formative and summative evaluations (c) Able understand the ability of students, (d) Able to use learning facilities and infrastructure (e) Understand learning strategies, and (f). Able to achieve learning goals.

4.4.2. Teacher's Positive Attitude Towards the Profession

Based on the results of the observations⁴⁶, it was seen that the teacher of cooking before the implementation of the learning activities took place, the cookery teacher first entered the cookery laboratory. In addition to the disciplinary attitude shown through coming to class on time, the teacher also seemed able to overcome the problems faced by students in the form of limited facilities and infrastructure as well as limited capital.

According to K⁴⁷: One of the obstacles faced was limited equipment such as the absence of electricity, water and capital installations, with minimal capital the teacher emphasized the students so that students were serious in the production process and minimized mistakes in the production process. Furthermore, the results of the author's observation⁴⁸, it is known that the teacher seeks to show his sense of responsibility to achieve the learning goals by taking the initiative to increase his teaching hours from 09.00 WIB-15.00 WIB. N2⁴⁹ revealed, "I am interested in participating in the development of catering, because in addition to equipping me with knowledge about how to process healthy food, I also want to open a cake shop business. I am interested in a devout endeavor to serve as a teacher besides teaching Mrs. K to also have a cake shop side business. "

From the results of interviews, observation and documentation, it can be concluded that the cookery teacher already has the appearance of a positive attitude, namely: The teacher has a stable and stable personality by providing exemplary through discipline which is shown by the teacher to have the initiative to solve the problem of limited facilities and infrastructure, having openness in thinking by expressing his opinion on the importance of adding learning time to having a positive attitude, being respected by students and being a role model for students.

4.4.3. Having the ability to adjust to the work environment

IG⁵⁰ confirmed, In general, the social competence of good culinary teachers, attended each meeting held by Islamic boarding schools and was able to provide positive input related to the development of culinary learning. Furthermore, K⁵¹ said, the obstacles found in learning activities were

⁴⁶ Observation at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara District Jambi Province Jambi October 15 2018.

⁴⁷ K, Guru Tata Boga, Pondok Pesantren Nurul Iman Kabupaten Muara Jambi, 15 Oktober 2018.

⁴⁸ Observation at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara District Jambi Province Jambi October 15 2018.

⁴⁹ N2, Students, Interview, Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara District Jambi Province Jambi October 15 2018.

⁵⁰ IG, School leader, Interview at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara Jambi Regency Jambi Province, 18 October 2018.

⁵¹ K, cook teacher, Interview, Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara District Jambi Province Jambi October 15 2018.

communicated through monthly meetings and the leadership responded positively to and planned to open a bakery.⁵²

From the data above, it can be concluded that culinary teachers have the ability to adjust to the work environment. This is based on the following indicators: the teacher is able to communicate in the scientific community, that is, the teacher is able to put himself into another group of people able to convey his arguments in meetings held by the boarding school.

5. Conclusion

- 1) The leadership of the boarding school plans the facilities and infrastructure before identifying the teacher, delegates the task of teaching cooking to qualified teachers, and provides curriculum autonomy, scheduling schedules and funding.
- 2) In organizing activities, the head of the lodge places himself as a supervisor, and instructs the principal as the supervisor and person in charge, the chairman of the entrepreneurial coordinator as the driver, and the teacher as the implementer.
- 3) In the implementation activities the leader instructs the head of the school so that the teacher prepares the syllabus and lesson plan, optimizes himself to be a mentor and counselor, completes class administration, and develops learning evaluation
- 4) The supervisory activities include direct supervision by looking directly at the implementation of indirect learning and supervision activities by looking through curriculum documents.

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⁵² Observation at Nurul Iman Islamic Boarding School in Muara District Jambi Province Jambi October 15 2018.

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